

Fisher's Information and Probability Dictated by Physics and Not Vice Versa?

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Given a coin, one has two complementary pieces of information and a corresponding probability of .5 and .5. Similar considerations apply to a die. As a result, one may get the impression that there exists a unique probability distribution in a probabilistic system and that this single probability scheme is linked to the constrained maximization of Shannon's entropy or Fisher's information. We argue however, that there may be different probability schemes in the same problem associated with different pieces of information which are relevant to the physics which occurs in the system. Thus, we argue that it is the physics which selects the probability distribution to be examined. For example, one may loosely think in terms of a detailed probability scheme versus a kind-of coarse grained one in the same system. For example, for a quantum free particle, $P(x)=1$ i.e there is the same probability for a particle to be at any x point. This, however, is based on velocity, i.e. the relationship between dx and dt . There is another piece of information in the system, namely m_0 which together with v yields momentum (either relativistic or nonrelativistic) . This need not be measured using a clock (which velocity requires), but by the impact of an impulse on a target. Thus, nonrelativistically $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ give the same impulse, but have different velocities. Quantum mechanics shows that a free particle is governed by $\exp(ipx)$ which contains two unnormalized probability distributions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. These are key for impulse interactions (i.e. the physics of interactions such as with a 2-slit apparatus etc), yet $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$ maps into the "coarse-grained" $P(x)=\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) / L = \text{constant}$.

$P(x)$ is one probability scheme in the problem and $\exp(ipx)$ another (for a free particle). Each answers some physical questions, but one needs to know which probability to use (i.e. what information is relevant) to a particular situation. $P(x)$ is relevant to motion in space not involving interactions. $\exp(ipx)$ is relevant to interactions (even with a magnetic vector potential causing no magnetic field) or with a 2-slit apparatus. Furthermore, in a quantum bound state, one has $W^*(x)W(x) = P(x)$ ($W(x)=\text{wavefunction} = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$) and $a^*(p)a(p) = P(p)$. Each probability scheme corresponds to the analysis of a different kind of measurement, but various schemes may also be linked. Thus one may have to start with one to create the others. For example, $\exp(ipx)$ is the base for creating $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$, which ultimately yields $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$.

As a result, we argue that if probability exists in a system, it is not necessarily the case that there is a unique probability distribution. There may be various probability schemes linked with different information and different measurements/interactions. Thus, physics leads one to focus on a specific probability scheme. As a result, we argue that one must be careful when discussing pure statistical quantities and their extremization, because these quantities, like Shannon's entropy and Fisher's information, contain a classical probability distribution, but they do not indicate which distribution to use in the case that a system has more than one.

. As a result, the analysis of a system requires knowledge of the physics (interactions) occurring. We argue against thinking in terms of physics following directly from statistical considerations. The constrained extremization of one statistical quantity may yield a probability distribution related to one piece of information, but not to another. Furthermore, Shannon's

entropy and Fisher's information pertain to classical probability $0 \leq P(x) < 1$ and $\int P(x) dx = 1$. The wavefunction, $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$, is comprised of two probability distributions and ADD and MULTIPLIES statistically (i.e. OR and AND) situations, but is involved in relative average calculations because it is not normalized. It is also different because it allows for positive and negative values. These are properties which do not follow from statistics using a classical $P(x)$.

Lack of Uniqueness of a Probability Distribution

Classical probability is often associated with tosses of a fair coin or die. The information here is unique (heads or tails) or (1-6) and so are the associated probabilities. Thus, one may think in terms of "the probability" in the problem. What, however, if a problem has multiple probabilities? These may be related as in the case of a microscopic probability and its coarse grained (so-to-speak) version. In other words, there may be different probability distributions related to different measurements. For example, in a quantum bound state it is well-known that there are at least two probabilities:

$P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$ ((1a)) and $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ ((1b)) where $W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$

$P(p)$ is used to determine the probability of knocking out a particle with momentum p . There is no information about the x position of this particle. $P(x)$ is related to measuring spatial density. There is no information about the average momentum. Underlying both of these, however, is a third unnormalized nonclassical probability scheme $\exp(ipx)$ for a free particle.

Consider the free particle in more detail. If one examines $dx/dt = \text{constant}$, then for fixed dx , dt must also be constant. This gives rise to the flat distribution $P(x) = \text{constant}$ indicating that all x points carry the same weight. It is known, however, that this is a kind of coarse-grained probability associated with the measurable information v , because it does not explain two-slit interference. In such a case, one uses the probability $\exp(ipx)$ which is based on the information p which does not uniquely determine v . Thus the amount of time required for a particle to move across dx is not the physically important quantity in an impulse reaction, rather $p = mv$ (nonrelativistic) or $p = mv / \sqrt{1-v^2}$ ($c=1$) is. There is a probability scheme $\exp(ipix)$ (which is not classical probability) describing an impulse that maps to $P(x) = 1/L$ through $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$ $\exp(-ipx)/\sqrt{L}$.

Thus one cannot necessarily ask: What is the probability distribution in the system? One should associate it with the measurement of a specific kind of information. This piece of information may be involved in certain types of interactions or relationships which are linked to the specific probability and in turn to constrained extremizations of various statistical quantities. For example, one may extremize Fisher's information for a bound state quantum state with the constraints $V(x)W(x)W(x)$ and $W(x)W(x)$, to obtain the time-independent Schrodinger equation (1), but Fisher's information is 0 for $P(x) = \text{constant}$. $P(x) = \text{constant}$, however, describes the coarse-grained velocity dependent probability of a free particle. So why doesn't constrained Fisher's information extremization handle $P(x) = \text{constant}$? We argue that one must be careful

when using the extremization of statistical quantities using a probability distribution in a completely arbitrary way.

Another example of a lack of uniqueness and consequences on Fisher's information is classical. Fisher's information is given by:

$$I = \text{constant} \int dx P(x) \left\{ \frac{d}{dx} \ln(P) \right\} \left\{ \frac{d}{dx} \ln(P) \right\} \quad ((2))$$

$P(x) > 0$ so one may write: $P(x) = f(x)f(x)$. Then:

$$I = \text{constant} \int dx \frac{df}{dx} \frac{df}{dx} \quad ((3))$$

This form ((3)) applies to both the time-independent Schrodinger equation with $df/dx = dW/dx$ and to a classical nonrelativistic Lagrangian $df/dx = dx/dt$. One may extremize ((3)) with $df/dx = dx/dt$ and constant = $m/2$ to find the solution of a free classical particle i.e.

$-d/dt^2 dx/dt = 0$ ((4)) where an integration by parts has been used to convert $\int dx/dt^2 dx/dt$ into ((4))

For a potential, one adds the constraint $(V-E)f(x)f(x)$

A problem, we argue, is that a bound classical system may also be said to have a spatial density $P(x) = C/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is taken to be positive i.e. one considers half of the path. From a statistical point of view, $P(x)$ is a perfectly fine probability distribution, but constrained Fisher's extremization no longer works i.e.

$\sqrt{P} = \sqrt{C}/\sqrt{v}$ and extremization with the constraint $(V-E)\sqrt{P}\sqrt{P}$ yields:

Then one extremizes the first term: constant $C \left\{ \int dx \left(\frac{d}{dx} \frac{1}{\sqrt{v}} \right) \left(\frac{d}{dx} \frac{1}{\sqrt{v}} \right) \right\} \rightarrow$

$-C \text{ constant } \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{1}{\sqrt{v}} = -.75C \text{ constant } v \text{ (power } -5/2)$

The constraint $(V-E)\sqrt{P}\sqrt{P}$ yields: $C^2(V-E) \sqrt{P}$ so the first term is of the order:

Velocity (power -2) when it should be vv i.e. kinetic energy. Furthermore, one may ask why a statistical extremization approach yields a nonrelativistic result and not a relativistic one which is more general.

The point we wish to make is that one may not arbitrarily choose a probability in a system because there may be more than one. Statistical extremization problems contain "a probability", but they don't indicate which one to choose. Thus it seems that there must be very specific physics associated with the extremization of a statistical extremization approach and one needs to know this physics.

Quantum Free Particle and Quantum Bound State

A quantum bound state is based on a $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$, where $W(x)$ is real and $P(x)$ is a classical probability. In (1), constrained Fisher's information is applied to:

Constant Integral dW/dx dW/dx dx with the constraint $(V(x)-E) W(x)W(x)$ to yield:

$$-\text{Constant } dW/dx \frac{dW/dx}{W(x)} + V(x)W(x) = EW(x) \quad ((4))$$

We ask: Why does this yield the nonrelativistic, instead of more general relativistic case? In principle, it seems one could use a different constraint namely: $\{ (E-V)(E-V) - \text{momo} \} WW$ and then obtain the Klein-Gordon equation with a potential $V(x)$.

A more disturbing issue is that for $P(x)=\text{constant}$, Fisher's information is 0 and so may not be extremized, but this is the free particle quantum case which, we argue, is the basis for much of quantum mechanics. How can a general statistical constrained extremization process bypass the fundamental free particle case? Furthermore, for a free particle, one may not write $P(x)=f(x)f(x)$, rather one writes $P(x) = \exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ and not $f(x)$ is the probability distribution in question.

We ask: Is there a connection between Fisher's information extremization and $\exp(ipx)$? We argue there is. $P(x)=\text{constant}$ at each x may be satisfied by the sum of two positive distribution functions which are unnormalized i.e.

$$\cos(px)\cos(px) + \sin(px) \sin(px) = 1 \quad ((5))$$

Thus $P(x)=\text{constant}$ may be a coarse-grained result of a more complicated situation which involves two x -probability distributions $\cos(px)$, $\sin(px)$ which account for the momentum and its sign (direction of motion). This probability distribution describes the physics of impulses, we argue. In such a case, we note that one has: $P(x) + 1-P(x) = 1$ (obvious) and $P(x)$ periodic.

Consider only $P(x) + 1-P(x) = 1$ i.e. a two dimensional scheme. Let $P=ff$ and $1-P=gg$. Then:

$$fdf/dx = -g dg/dx \quad \text{or:} \quad df/dx / f = - dg/dx / g \quad ((6))$$

For example, ((6)) holds for $P(x)=x/b$ and $1-P=1-x/b$.

Next, consider the sum of the Fisher's information of these two classical probabilities.

$$I(P(x)) + I(1-P(x)) = \frac{dP/dx}{P} \frac{dP/dx}{P} + \frac{dP/dx}{(1-P)} \frac{dP/dx}{(1-P)} = \frac{dP/dx}{P(1-P)} \frac{dP/dx}{P(1-P)} \quad ((7))$$

These are two relative probabilities i.e. dP/dx is the change in P divided by the value of P etc.

If ((7)) is considered to be a constant i.e. does not distinguish one x from another then:

$$dP/dx / P = (1-P) / dP/dx \quad ((8a)) \quad \text{or} \quad 2 df/dx / f = .5 g / dg/dx \quad ((8b))$$

One may see that $P=x/b$ does not satisfy ((8)). ((8b)) suggests a solution related to: $df/dx = g$ which leads to periodicity. Thus, we argue that Fisher's information and its extremization are linked to periodicity i.e. $d/dx \cos(px) = -C \sin(px)$ (similar expression for \sin) are of the form of Fisher information extremizations for $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ by themselves. This may be why Fisher information extremization is associated with quantum mechanics. It is not simply the case of statistics giving rise to physics as $\exp(ipx)$ may be obtained as the eigenfunction of the translation generator $-id/dx$ with no considerations of statistics.

Wavefunction as a kind-of Probability

It is interesting that extremization of Fisher's information (1) begins with a classical probability $P(x)$. One then writes: $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$. There are also approaches in the literature which begin with a continuity equation in $P(x)$, but then write $P(x) = f(x)f^*(x)$ where $f(x) = \sqrt{\text{density}}\exp(iS(x))$ where $S(x)$ is a function of x . In both of these cases, one has the AND/OR multiply/divide rule for $P(x)$ which is a probability, but this does not carry over to $W(x)$ or $f(x)$ because it is not formally defined as a probability. Nevertheless, $W(x)$ adds like a probability and also multiplies in an AND situation. Thus we consider $W(x)$ to be a nonclassical probability and not simply a "kind of square root" of a classical probability. We cite this as a problem with probability theories which start with $P(x)$ and do not recognize $W(x)$ as a probability as well, albeit one that is unnormalized and hence based on relative averages. For example:

A free particle has a p and pp which are calculated using: $p \exp(ipx)/\exp(ipx)$ and $pp \exp(ipx)/\exp(ipx)$ i.e. using a relative scheme.

$$\text{For } W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \rightarrow \langle pp \rangle = \{\text{Sum over } p \ pp \ a(p)\exp(ipx)\} / W(x) \quad ((9))$$

$a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ summed over p equals 1 and acts as a conditional probability. We argue that adding $\exp(ipx)$ s for a 2-slit interference interaction or other impulse situations is not a "new rule", but the usual addition of probabilities rule for an unusual probability which is complex(two dimensional) with each component taking on positive and negative values. We argue that this is not a result which follows from constrained extremization of statistical quantities expressed in terms of classical probability $P(x)$.

Reflection/Refraction in One Dimension

As a final example of two probability distributions in the same problem, with one being "coarse-grained" so to speak, we consider one dimensional reflection-refraction at $x=0$ the interface of media with $n=\text{index of refraction}=1$ and $n_2>n_1$. There is probability because a single photon may reflect or refract. There exists a probability distribution associated with counting which is linked to reflection/refraction probabilities i.e.

$$AA/c1 = BB/c1 + CC/c2 \quad ((10))$$

Here AA is the incident intensity, BB the reflected and CC the refracted. Intensity is written as AA to show it is positive. If AA=1, then BB and CC are classical probabilities. ((10)) is a conservation of energy and number of photons equation. The classical probability description AA, BB, CC suffices for “counting” which is one kind of measurement. Unfortunately it does not describe the entire physics of the problem. This probability does not contain enough information so to speak. It does not deal with interactions which are key i.e. the impulses involved. To think in terms of interactions, one may write ((10)) as:

$AA/c1 - BB/c1 = CC/c2$ and obtain two equations (using $E=p1c1 = p2c2$) using a difference of squares:

$$A+B = C \quad ((11a)) \quad \text{and} \quad p1A-p1B = p2C \quad ((11b))$$

A, B, C become a set of new probabilities which solve the problem. In other words, one does not have a unique probability scheme, even though the two probabilities are linked in that one is the “square root” of the other. (Actually $A \exp(ip1x)$ etc hold here, so one really takes the modulus instead of squaring.)

The physics (in this case the impulses and continuity of A, B, C) determine the probability scheme which applies. In other words, simply because there is probability in a problem, does not mean one knows the appropriate probability distribution. The form ((11b)) used for counting, which indicates probability, contains the “square” probability. This does not contain enough information to solve the problem. It is the “square root” probability, a different, but linked probability, which solves the problem and is linked to periodicity.

This periodicity is a physical property and if a statistical quantity, such as Fisher’s information, may be linked to it as described ((8b)), there may be a link between statistics and physics, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a given physical system may be linked with more than one probability distribution. The different probability distributions are associated with different kinds of measurements of information. When focusing on a problem, one must choose the information which describes the “essential” physics of the problem, for example interactions/impulse instead of counting. As a result, this is not a pure statistical situation. In quantum mechanics, we argue that the root of the picture is based on impulse. One needs a probability scheme which describes the impulse scenario. Once this is found, one may create other somewhat “coarse-grained” probabilities from it. For example, the wavefunction is the nonclassical probability which describes impulses and from it one may obtain $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ and $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$ where $W(x)= \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

Constrained extremization of statistical quantities which contain a classical probability bypass the notion of a nonclassical probability, such as $W(x)$. Furthermore, given multiple probabilities

in a problem, they do not indicate which one to choose. Thus we argue that when using these approaches, one needs to be aware of the physics in the problem and how it pertains to a statistical quantity. For example, we try to show that Fisher's information is linked with periodicity which is also present in $\exp(ipx)$ the free particle quantum nonclassical probability. Thus, there may be a link between extremizing Fisher's information and $\exp(ipx)$ or its constituents $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$, which is in fact the case.

References

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